

Call 2 link to the Euraxess website

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D3.2 CALL 2 LINK TO THE EURAXESS WEBSITE

Grant Agreement n°:	101126533
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Project acronym:	TOUCH
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Project title:	Towards the next generatiOn of excellent yoUng doctoral researchers on mental health by developing an intersectoral & transdisciplinary approaCH
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Funding Scheme:	MSCA-COFUND-2022 (DOCTORAL PROGRAMME)
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Project Duration:	2024/02/01 – 2029/01/31 (60 months)
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Beneficiary:	Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona (UAB)
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Implementing partners:	Centre d'Estudis Demogràfics (CED) Centre de Recerca Matemàtica (CRM) Centre de Visió per Computador (CVC) Fundació Salut i Envel·liment (FSIE) Institut d'Investigació i Innovació Parc Taulí (I3PT) Institut de Recerca Sant Pau (IR Sant Pau) Vall d'Hebron Institut de Recerca (VHIR)
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Project no. 101126533

TOUCH

Towards the next generatiOn of excellent yoUng doctoral researchers on mental health by developing an intersectoral & transdisciplinary approaCH

MSCA-COFUND-2022 (DOCTORAL PROGRAMME)

Start date of project: 01/02/2024 Duration: 60 months

History Chart				
Issue	Date	Changed page(s)	Cause of change	Implemented by
1.0	22/1/2025	-	Draft	UAB
2.0	27/1/2025	-	Version 2.0	UAB

Validation			
No.	Action	Beneficiary	Date
1	Prepared	UAB	21 January 2025
2	Approved	UAB	26 January 2025
3	Released	UAB	27 January 2025

Disclaimer

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Call 2 link to the EURAXESS website

The job offers for the second call of the TOUCH programme were published on the EURAXESS website on 21 January 2025. The announcement included all the information required for candidates to apply for the available positions. It provided a detailed description of the predoctoral programme, research and training activities, partner institutions, eligibility criteria, employment conditions, and selection process. Clear instructions on how to apply through the [TOUCH website](#) were also provided. The job advertisement is accessible via the following link on the EURAXESS platform: [EURAXESS Post](#), and is reproduced in Annex 1: TOUCH EURAXESS announcement.

Call 2 links to the individual offer's posts on EURAXESS

In addition to the main TOUCH announcement, each of the 21 projects available in the second call was published individually on the EURAXESS portal on 21-22 January 2025. Along with the general information outlined above, these individual posts offered a comprehensive overview of each research project, including details about the supervisors, research groups, and the skills and qualifications required for a competitive application. The links to each job advertisement and their respective publication dates are provided in Table 1. A screenshot of the TOUCH EURAXESS account, showing the publication details of the job offers, can be found in Annex 2: job offers published on EURAXESS.

Table 1: list of TOUCH job offers for the second call, including links to their EURAXESS publications and publication dates.

TOPIC (INSTITUTION)	LINK	PUBLICATION DATE
Link between the consumption of ultra-processed foods and drinks and major depressive (UAB)	https://euraxess.ec.europa.eu/jobs/310046	21 January 2025
Developing New Models and Measures of Genetic and Psychological Sensitivity to the Psychosocial Environment to Understand both Risk and Resilience in Mental Health (UAB)	https://euraxess.ec.europa.eu/jobs/310056	21 January 2025
Cognitive and Metabolic impact in Patients with Affective Disorders: deciphering moderating factors for achieving better outcomes (UAB)	https://euraxess.ec.europa.eu/jobs/310063	21 January 2025
Brain cell types and neuromodulators in fear memory models (UAB)	https://euraxess.ec.europa.eu/jobs/310069	21 January 2025
Urban Design, Mental Health, and Maternal Wellbeing (UAB)	https://euraxess.ec.europa.eu/jobs/310077	21 January 2025
Social Media Use and Young People's Mental Health: A Quantitative Social Science Approach (UAB)	https://euraxess.ec.europa.eu/jobs/310082	21 January 2025 (updated on 23 January 2025)
The political philosophy of mental health as a public health issue (UAB)	https://euraxess.ec.europa.eu/jobs/310095	21 January 2025
Narrative Bodies: Literary and Philosophical Approaches to Mental Health Across Lifespan Transitions (UAB)	https://euraxess.ec.europa.eu/jobs/310119	21 January 2025

Body, Space, and Care: Philosophical and Literary Interventions in Mental Health Determinants (UAB)	https://euraxess.ec.europa.eu/jobs/310123	21 January 2025
Linguistic deficits in children with Autism Spectrum Disorder (UAB)	https://euraxess.ec.europa.eu/jobs/310125	21 January 2025
Enriched Stroke Rehabilitation through Music and Leisure Activities: Exploring recovery, brain biomarkers, and aspects for implementation (UAB)	https://euraxess.ec.europa.eu/jobs/310130	21 January 2025
Mental health and multimorbidity in Catalonia (CED)	https://euraxess.ec.europa.eu/jobs/310160	21 January 2025
Mental health and mortality in the context of ageing societies (CED)	https://euraxess.ec.europa.eu/jobs/310162	21 January 2025
Modelling circular inference, from the general population to psychotic experience (CRM)	https://euraxess.ec.europa.eu/jobs/310296	22 January 2025
Computational modeling of working memory decline in normal and pathological aging (CRM)	https://euraxess.ec.europa.eu/jobs/310298	22 January 2025
Enhancing Elderly Mental Health through maintaining cognitive status and preventing delirium during hospitalization by multicomponent intervention led by Geriatrics (FSIE)	https://euraxess.ec.europa.eu/jobs/310299	22 January 2025
Intergenerational transmission of psychopathology: Effects of parental genotypes (VHIR)	https://euraxess.ec.europa.eu/jobs/310304	22 January 2025
Towards precision medicine in ADHD and depression: a genetic approach (VHIR)	https://euraxess.ec.europa.eu/jobs/310307	22 January 2025
Prevention, follow-up and management of post-ICU sequelae based on digital health tools (I3PT)	https://euraxess.ec.europa.eu/jobs/310309	22 January 2025
Integrative Omics and Neuroimaging in Treatment-Resistant Depression: An Artificial Intelligence-Driven Approach (IR Sant Pau)	https://euraxess.ec.europa.eu/jobs/310317	22 January 2025
Caregiver-Centric Innovations in Intensive Home-Treatment for Acute Mental Illness: A Comprehensive Approach (IR Sant Pau)	https://euraxess.ec.europa.eu/jobs/310320	22 January 2025

EURAXESS**Job offer****UAB****Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona**

JOB SPAIN

[Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona](#) | Posted on: 21 January 2025**11 PhD positions on mental health and wellbeing in the framework of the TOUCH COFUND project led by the Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona (UAB)**Apply now [\(https://webs.uab.cat/touch/\)](https://webs.uab.cat/touch/) [Add to Favorites](#) [Share](#)[View \(/jobs/310154\)](#) [Edit \(/node/310154/edit\)](#)

21 Jan 2025

Job Information**Organisation/Company**

TOUCH

Research FieldPsychological sciences
Neurosciences
Sociology
Demography
Biological sciences
Ethics in health sciences
Geography
Language sciences
Literature
Philosophy
Medical sciences**Researcher Profile**

First Stage Researcher (R1)

Positions	PhD Positions
Country	Spain
Application Deadline	31 Mar 2025 - 00:00 (Europe/Madrid)
Type of Contract	Temporary
Job Status	Full-time
Hours Per Week	37,5
Offer Starting Date	1 Feb 2025
Is the job funded through the EU Research Framework Programme?	Horizon Europe – COFUND
Marie Curie Grant Agreement Number	101126533
Is the Job related to staff position within a Research Infrastructure?	No

Offer Description

The [TOUCH](#) doctoral programme is offering 11 three-year pre-doctoral fellowships. TOUCH (“Towards the next generatiOn of excellent yoUng doctoral researchers on mental health by developing an intersectoral & transdisciplinary approaCH”) is a new excellent doctoral programme coordinated by the [Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona](#) (UAB) and co-funded by the Marie Skłodowska-Curie (MSCA) Actions of the European Commission. Its main goal is the recruitment and training of doctoral candidates in the field of **mental health and wellbeing** providing a new dimension through highly interdisciplinary and intersectoral research while fulfilling all the principles of Open Science and maintaining the highest research quality standards. TOUCH involves the UAB and 7 reference organisations as implementing partners hosting doctoral students (research centres, research foundations and research organisations linked to prestigious hospitals in the region): [Centre d'Estudis Demogràfics](#), [Centre de Recerca Matemàtica](#), [Centre de Visió per Computador](#), [Fundació Salut i Envel·liment UAB](#), [Institut d'Investigació i Innovació Parc Taulí](#), [Institut de Recerca Sant Pau](#), and [Vall d'Hebron Institut de Recerca](#).

We are looking for candidates with an **excellent CV**, a high degree of **ambition and motivation**, and with **good personal qualities** to join the TOUCH doctoral programme. We offer a three-year full-time contract (37,5 hours / week) starting at the end of 2025 and a gross salary of 28.500 €/year (the salary will be the same for the 3 years). Tuition fees will be covered by the project. The successful candidates will be enrolled in a doctoral program at the UAB and will be involved in the TOUCH training activities, including: (i) workshops and practical hands-on schools, (ii) training in scientific and communication skills, research diversity and a personal development retreat, among other activities to bring a holistic approach to the training through a combination of research-oriented and challenging soft skills, and (iii) international and/or intersectoral secondments at partner laboratories and premises.

The candidates must fulfil the following eligibility criteria from the EC: **Mobility rule:** candidates must not have resided or carried out their main activity (work, studies, etc.) in Spain for more than 12 months in the 36 months immediately preceding the deadline for the programme call. **Experience rule:** researchers must be doctoral candidates at the date of recruitment, i.e. not already in possession of a doctoral degree at the deadline of the open calls. Researchers who have successfully defended their doctoral thesis but have not yet formally awarded the doctoral degree will not be considered eligible. **The candidates must hold a degree that allows admission to the official doctoral programme at UAB.** Additional academic and skills requirements for each position can be found in the “offered PhD positions” section on the [TOUCH website](#).

Interested applicants should apply through the TOUCH online platform by submitting a full CV, a motivation letter, two letters of recommendation and academic and English level certificates. The call will be open from the 1st of February to the 31st of March 2025. More information about the TOUCH project, the recruitment process, and the application platform are available on the [TOUCH website](#).

Where to apply

Website <https://webs.uab.cat/touch/>

Requirements

Research Field	Psychological sciences
Education Level	Master Degree or equivalent
Research Field	Neurosciences
Education Level	Master Degree or equivalent
Research Field	Medical sciences
Education Level	Master Degree or equivalent
Research Field	Sociology
Education Level	Master Degree or equivalent

Research Field	Biological sciences
Education Level	Master Degree or equivalent
Research Field	Demography
Education Level	Master Degree or equivalent
Research Field	Economics
Education Level	Master Degree or equivalent
Research Field	Language sciences
Education Level	Master Degree or equivalent
Research Field	Philosophy
Education Level	Master Degree or equivalent
Research Field	Sociology
Education Level	Master Degree or equivalent
Research Field	Mathematics
Education Level	Master Degree or equivalent
Research Field	Ethics in health sciences
Education Level	Master Degree or equivalent
Languages	ENGLISH
Level	Excellent

Additional Information

Work Location(s)

Number of offers available	11
Company/Institute	Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona
Country	Spain
Geofield	

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Contact

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Annex 2: TOUCH job offers published on EURAXESS

EURAXESS

[View \(/partnering/organisations/profile/universitat-autonoma-de-barcelona-6\)](/partnering/organisations/profile/universitat-autonoma-de-barcelona-6)
[Offers \(/group/7384/nodes\)](/group/7384/nodes)

[List of](#)

UAB
Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona

SPAIN

HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTION | SPAIN

Universitat Autonoma de Barcelona

Help on managing your organisation profile (</my/help/organisation-profile>).

Add Job Offer + **Add Funding** + **Add Hosting** +

Displaying 1 - 22 of 22

Title	Content type	Status	Moderation state	Updated	Views \ Apply
PhD position at the Institut de Recerca Sant Pau funded by the TOUCH COFUND project	Job Offer	Published	Published	22/01/2025 - 10:10	
PhD position at the Institut de Recerca Sant Pau funded by the TOUCH COFUND project	Job Offer	Published	Published	22/01/2025 - 10:08	
PhD position at the Institut de Recerca i Innovació Parc Taulí (I3PT) funded by the TOUCH COFUND project	Job Offer	Published	Published	22/01/2025 - 10:01	
PhD position at the Institut de Recerca Vall d'Hebron (VHIR) funded by the TOUCH COFUND project	Job Offer	Published	Published	22/01/2025 - 10:01	
PhD position at the Institut de Recerca Vall d'Hebron (VHIR) funded by the TOUCH COFUND project	Job Offer	Published	Published	22/01/2025 - 10:00	
PhD position at the Fundació Salut i Envel·liment (FSIE) funded by the TOUCH COFUND project	Job Offer	Published	Published	22/01/2025 - 09:58	
PhD position at Centre de Recerca Matemàtica (CRM)	Job Offer	Published	Published	22/01/2025 - 09:58	

Title	Content type	Status	Moderation state	Updated	Views \ Apply
funded by the TOUCH COFUND project					
PhD position at Centre de Recerca Matemàtica (CRM), funded by the TOUCH COFUND project	Job Offer	Published	Published	22/01/2025 - 08:39	
PhD position at Centre d'Estudis Demogràfics (CED), funded by the TOUCH COFUND project	Job Offer	Published	Published	21/01/2025 - 16:22	
PhD position at Centre d'Estudis Demogràfics (CED), funded by the TOUCH COFUND project	Job Offer	Published	Published	21/01/2025 - 16:18	
11 PhD positions on mental health and wellbeing in the framework of the TOUCH COFUND project led by the Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona (UAB).	Job Offer	Published	Published	21/01/2025 - 15:59	
PhD position at Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona (UAB), funded by the TOUCH COFUND project	Job Offer	Published	Published	21/01/2025 - 14:58	
PhD position at Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona (UAB).	Job Offer	Published	Published	21/01/2025 - 14:54	

Title	Content type	Status	Moderation state	Updated	Views \ Apply
funded by the TOUCH COFUND project					
PhD position at Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona (UAB) funded by the TOUCH COFUND project	Job Offer	Published	Published	21/01/2025 - 14:53	
PhD position at Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona (UAB) funded by the TOUCH COFUND project	Job Offer	Published	Published	21/01/2025 - 14:44	
PhD position at Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona (UAB) funded by the TOUCH COFUND project	Job Offer	Published	Published	21/01/2025 - 14:30	
PhD position at Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona (UAB) funded by the TOUCH COFUND project	Job Offer	Published	Published	21/01/2025 - 14:03	
PhD position at Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona (UAB) funded by the TOUCH COFUND project	Job Offer	Published	Published	21/01/2025 - 14:02	
PhD position at Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona (UAB) funded by the TOUCH	Job Offer	Published	Published	21/01/2025 - 14:01	

Title	Content type	Status	Moderation state	Updated	Views \ Apply
COFUND project					
PhD position at Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona (UAB), funded by the TOUCH COFUND project	Job Offer	Published	Published	21/01/2025 - 13:58	
PhD position at Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona (UAB), funded by the TOUCH COFUND project	Job Offer	Published	Published	21/01/2025 - 13:56	
PhD position at Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona (UAB), funded by the TOUCH COFUND project	Job Offer	Published	Published	21/01/2025 - 13:53	